

EDUCATION TRANSFER KNOWLEDGE 12.

Development of training of school and
academic mentors, and student teachers

Project Information

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1. INTRODUCTION

Following the development of the contents and activities (Output 11) for the small private online course (SPOC), **University College of Teacher Education Vienna** has taken on the role of development of the framework for training key school placement (SP) actors - student teachers (prospective teachers), academic mentors (university tutors, lectures) and school mentors (school teachers, cooperating teachers, mentors). This constitutes **EKT Pilot Preparation Phase**.

The EKT Pilot Preparation Phase, the training process, has **four key aims**:

- Introduce the course participants with the EKT system;
- Start coordination and communication processes prior to the in-school placement between academic mentors (university tutors), student teachers, and school teachers (school mentors);
- Start reflective process by reflecting on student teachers' expectations for the in-school placement;
- Start an inquiry process that could be developed during the in-school placement experience via observation, professional dialogue, teaching probes, and critical reflection.

The technical side of the training process has also its aims: 1) to have all the users registered prior to the in-school placement; 2) to have the EKT Tools tried out before the in-school placement.

All in all, the training phase is seen as an important element of the EKT Pilot. In the next section, the EKT Pilot Preparation Phase (Training) is described in detail. It should be mentioned that prior to the Training Process, a number of actions are necessary: 1) briefing sessions with university tutors, student teachers and school mentors; 2) registering all the participants on the platform; 3) setting the course and prepare the EKT content on the Platform. For this, PHW team together with the Industry Partners have prepared the Guidelines (see Appendix A).

2. TRAINING PROCESS

The preparation phase for the EKT pilot, the training, comprises of a series of 7 steps that need to be undertaken by the academic mentors (university tutor), the student teacher, and school mentors. Training on the EKT system and methodology takes place mainly before the in-school placement, however the whole course or part of it can be conducted when student teachers go to schools. The following diagram presents the flow of the Training Development (Figure 1).

Figure 1: EKT Training Process.

The following table outlines each of the 7 steps in detail.

Table 1: Training Process

Step	Description	Responsibility
1. SPOC Preparation	University coordinators (tutors) set up the courses and organize the Training space on the Chamilo LMS for groups following instructions. Depending on the partners' needs there can be one or more courses created. This depends on grouping student teachers for ePortfolios since ePortfolio is seen as part of Training. It can be a year group, or a group for each university tutor (academic mentor), or using other relevant criteria to divide student teachers into groups.	University coordinators or pilot coordinators
2. SPOC Guide	University coordinators (or tutors) may send a short SPOC Guide with the information where to find the course on the Platform to all the participants (if this is not explained during meetings or as an additional assisting tool).	University or Pilot coordinators
3. Analysing SPOC Contents	It is recommended for university tutors (academic mentors) to look at the tasks of the SPOC prior to meeting their students and school mentors. This is helpful for academic mentors to know the contents and tasks of the SPOC, as well as to understand the capacities of the EKT Platform in order to instruct and engage student teachers and school mentors in a meaningful way. Moreover, if academic mentors envision it they can pre-create a shared folder with required documents, or set the calendar and share these with student teachers and school mentors, in other words start using the EKT Platform for coordination purposes from the start.	University tutors (academic mentors) with support of pilot coordinators
4. UNIT 1. Introduction to EKT Platform	Unit 1 should be completed prior to the start of the in-school placement, and is seen as the preparation phase for the in-school placement. Its key focus is on using the EKT Tools for communication, file management, and time management; as well as on reflecting on in-school expectations together with all the actors.	Academic mentors, student teachers, school mentors
5. UNIT 2. Action Research in the Classroom	Unit 2 can be completed prior or at the beginning of the in-school placement. The key aim of the Unit is to introduce the ePortfolio Tool and start reflective process. Unit 2 introduces the framework of action research for teachers, and highlights the importance of critical reflection. Student teachers are invited to reflect in their values, and write a blog on why they decided to become teachers; and to provides a framework for observation that can be used for their inquiry later.	Student teachers with mentors' support
6. UNIT 3. Focus on Reflection and Professional Dialogue	Unit 3 can be completed during the in-school placement, since all the actors are introduced to the EKT methodology and platform already. It is aimed to engage all the actors in critical reflection of teaching and in professional dialogue. This Unit should ground on situated experiences of student teachers, when student teachers reflect on their teaching probes or observations, and start a mini inquiry on finding solutions to a 'teaching' question they raise.	Student teachers with mentors' support Academic and school mentors guide student teachers in their inquiry. Academic and school mentors can use the EKT rubrics to evaluate student teachers' inquiry.
7. SPOC Survey	Training on the EKT System ends with SPOC Survey. It aims to understand the participants readiness to use the EKT Tools (Self-Efficacy Questionnaire), and evaluate the participants' satisfaction with the EKT Platform. The Survey includes ranking and open-ended questions	ALL

A note: For the second pilot, Unit 4 was added to introduce the course participants with the content development tool, Chamilo Studio. Unit 4 can be completed at any time by student teachers.

3. TRAINING TIMEFRAME AND COORDINATION WITH EKT PROJECT PARTNERS

The timeframe for each step is defined and agreed within the piloting University and communicated by the EKT Pilot Coordinator to the EKT project team.

During the partner meetings and pilot coordinators meetings PHW Team informed and prepared instructions for setting up the course space on the platform and explained the procedures and expectations.

The SPOC contents were translated into partner languages and accessible in English, German, Spanish and Portuguese. Pilot Coordinators task was to set up the courses on the partners' Chamilo space based on the 'Master course' PHW team has created, with the help of the industry partners and PHW Team.

Thus, the timeframe for training in each partner institution is given below. Since piloting happens in different timeframes depending on local contexts, training had to be adjusted to these needs.

Table 2: Training Timeframe in Partner Institutions

Partner Institution	Training Timeframe
Austria	September 2021 – January 2022 for various groups
Spain	First cycle <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 1 September 2021- 15 January 2022• 1 February-31 March 2022
	Second cycle <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 1 September 2022- 15 October 2022
Ireland	1 to 31 October 2022
UK	No data
Portugal	October 2022

4. NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

The following table (Table 3) present number of participants in each partner institution.

	Austria	Ireland	Portugal	Spain
How many participants registered for the course pilot?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 70 student teachers; 5 academic mentors 	10	28	First cycle (2021-22 academic year) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 23 student-teacher 23 School mentor 6 Academic mentor
	15 school mentors			Second cycle (2022-23 academic year) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 81 student-teacher 81 School mentor
How many of these completed the course?	29 student teachers	All completed the course - 10	Most trainees who participated in the pilot study did not complete the SPOC.	First cycle <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 23 student-teacher 23 School mentor Academic mentor
				Second cycle <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 81 student-teacher 81 School mentor
				Academic mentor

Table 4: Number of Course Participants

5. REWARDS

At the end of the course, participants are awarded a Certificate (Appendix B). This is a two-sides paper document signed by the Head of a Partner Institution, or a relevant person depending on piloting institutions contexts. To be awarded the Certificate, the expectation is to participate in the discussions in the EKT Chat; and submitted final task of the EKT SPOC to academic mentors. In most cases it was decided that academic mentors grant their student teachers the Certificate.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The overall aim of the EKT project was to transfer knowledge between schools, HEIs and industry, in the context of designing a platform and associated course to support student teachers on placement. During the development of training we relied greatly on the expertise, support and guidance of the industry partners. We also needed to understand the complexity of each partner institution context, and highlighted the need to adjust the training process to each piloting institution. There are a number of lessons learnt which are the focus of the present section.

Content relevance. The training programme was and should be aligned to the school placement objectives, in our case to the EKT methodology. Although one of the key objectives of the training was training on the EKT System, the pedagogical aspects were privileged. The training also aimed to provide opportunities for participants to collaborate and exchange ideas, experiences, research questions etc. These opportunities were put inside the structure of learning tasks that included discussion forums, portfolio, content creation. These were hoped to be meaningful and challenging.

Flexibility. The training process aimed to allow for adaptation to piloting institutions contexts in terms when and how long it could be run, in terms of assessment.

A variety of content assets. These include tutorial videos, content videos (on the EKT methodology and Action Research), Check-lists, Supportive Documents, Rubrics, Resources etc.

User Experience. To improve usability for the training, it was decided to simplify navigation by using direct links, making the tasks straightforward and as clear as possible.

Support. The participants were supported by PHW team and CESGA Team for technical issues. Technical issues required and got an immediate response. There were academic mentors to provide student teachers with guidance, and answer administrative and content questions. However, there is the need to incorporate into the experience mentors in a more engaged way who can offer constructive feedback and guidance on the projects, and exchanges on the forum.

Rewards and Incentives. The SPOC experience was thought as to be challenging and applicable to the participants' professional growth. The end result of the SPOC includes a certificate that participants can share through their career profiles.

7. APPENDIX A.

GUIDELINES TO SET UP

THE EKT ONLINE COURSE

Setting up the EKT Online Course

1. Go to app.ektproject.eu > When you have your users, groups and schools set up, choose 'Preliminary Training' in the side bar of the Management Tool, then click 'Create Preliminary Training' using the right upper button.

2. The new window will appear, fill in and save: For the Title, recommendation would be setting up the group names, or EKT Online Course Group 'Mentors names'; for the type - Private!!!, Quota - we usually set up 250MB
3. In the management Tool choose 'Preliminary Training'. You should be able to see the course you have created. You can already subscribe users to the course by clicking on the symbol:

Setting up the course

- Now click on the course to enter. You will see an empty course. Now we need to add the intro description and make some elements invisible

4. 1. Click on the Intro settings:

- Here you can use the logo, and a short description of the course aims, e.g. we used the following picture: https://ektproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/40175_withLogo_small-1-1024x721.jpg

And the text:

Welcome to the **online course** of the EKT Erasmus+ Project!

EKT is an international project and stands for “Educational Knowledge Transfer”.

This course aims to introduce you to the platform, which was specifically developed to support your “in-school placement” experience in **three areas**:

- Cooperation and collaboration between student teachers, academic mentors and school mentors
- Professional dialogue
- Reflective practice

Also, please join us on Twitter and Facebook.

Here is how it looks like:

- To insert a picture, click on the Image symbol and insert the link to the picture, adjust the parameters.

- Hiding the elements we don't need: the eye symbol. We need only Learning Path, Portfolio, Assessment.
- Setting Terms and Conditions: Settings > Access > Terms and Conditions: insert the text for the terms and conditions, and the logos links as images

Links to logos to use:

EKT logo https://ektproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/FINAL_ekt-logo_small.jpg

EC logo https://ektproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/logosbeneficiaireserasmusright_en.png

6. Importing the SPOC

6.1. Go to Learning Paths and click on the icon "Import AICC, SCORM and Chamilo learning path"

6.2. Select the Scorm zip file which can be download from: <https://cumulo.cesga.es/index.php/s/C4Wctj5o4ZeWQZq>

And click on the Upload button. It takes a bit of time to upload and at the end it show you the confirmation message and your Learning Path.

6.3. You can click on the name of the learning path to see it.

Setting up Chat Groups in the Communication Tool

7. Setting up the Course CHAT Groups in the EKT Tool Communication

In the course there are three chat discussions planned within each group. Unit 1. Anecdote: Task 5 Go to **“funny anecdote”** in the Communication Tool and write down an anecdote which describes a funny episode in your learning/teaching career. Comment on at least three anecdotes.

Unit 2. Discussion on Observation: Task 5 Reflect on the topic of observation in the classroom. Answer the questions **“What are important aspects and what might be challenges of having an observer in your classroom?”** Think about organisational issues like introducing the observer to the students, where the observer will sit, feedback of the observer, peer observation, etc.

Unit 3. Research Question: Task 2 Define your own research question; determined by your individual teaching context and research interest. Leave comments to three more people.

In order to set up the Chats, go to the Main Dashboard, Communication

Create a new group > add the related title (e.g. Unit 1. Anecdote) > add participants (e.g. of one group) > Save. You can save the link to the chat and insert it into the Document with Links in Unit 1 in the Learning path.

Attention! If you add here a link to the specific chat group, this will need to be changed every time you create a new course for a new group!!!

Exporting and Importing the Master Course

8. Exporting the Master Course and creating new courses for more groups

8. 1. In the Course, go to Backup element.

8. 2. Create Backup > Full Backup > the file will be downloaded

8. 3. Go to the Management Tool in the EKT System > create a new course > Steps 7-9

8. 4. Go to Backup in the new course > Backup Import > Full Backup

8. 5. The settings will transfer to the new Course, BUT! You will need to add Terms and Conditions yourself as this doesn't copy automatically!

!Remember to set up the chat groups for the new courses.

Setting up the Survey

9. Setting up the EKT Survey

For this, you need to create a new course, titled 'EKT Survey', it should be set as OPEN!!!

A screenshot of the 'New course' form in a software interface. The form has a header 'New course' and several input fields: 'Name' (containing 'EKT Survey'), 'Code' (containing 'Code'), 'Country' (a dropdown menu with 'Austria' selected), 'Type' (a dropdown menu with 'Open (platform visible)' selected and circled in red), 'Quota' (a dropdown menu with '100MB' selected), and 'Higher Education Institution affiliation' (a dropdown menu with 'Select university from the list...' selected). A blue sidebar with 'Overview' is visible on the left.

As an intro description, you can add a picture and the intro text – similar to what will be inserted to the learning path or sent to the participants:

Hier ist ein offener Kurs wo man den Zugang zur [EKT Kursumfrage](#) finden kann. Ziel dieser Umfrage ist es, die Qualität des Kurses und der EKT -Tools zu bewerten. Ihre Antworten werden vom Projektteam berücksichtigt, um die Inhalte zu verbessern und zu aktualisieren. Das Ausfüllen der Umfrage dauert ca. **10 Minuten**. Vielen Dank für Ihre Teilnahme am EKT-Projekt und Ihre Teilnahme an der Umfrage!

Go to the Element Survey. It is the only element that should be made visible.

Click Create Survey. Fill in the elements:

For **questions 1 -5**, it can be dropdown

For **question 6**, better Multiple Choice with other option

End of page

For **question 7 – 9/10** *we set from 1 to 5

End of page

For **question 8 – 9/10**

End of page

For **question 8,10** – open

End of page

For **question 11, 12** – open

Nº	Titel	Typ	Anzahl der Möglichkeiten	ändern
1	Land	Dropdown	5	
2	Geschlecht	Dropdown	3	
3	Alter	Dropdown	6	
4	Rolle im Kurs	Dropdown	3	
5	Für Mentor*innen und Praxisberater*innen: Arbeitserfahrung ...	Dropdown	5	
6	Für Studierende: Ausbildungsprogram ...	Dropdown	7	
7	Kurszufriedenheit	Seitenende (Trennt Fragen)	0	
8	Wie zufrieden waren Sie mit den folgenden Aspekten des Online Kurses (Kursaufbau, Methodik Und Inhal ...	Wert	7	
9	Die EKT Kursumgebung	Seitenende (Trennt Fragen)	0	
10	Die EKT Kursumgebung (Ich Kann Statements). Ich kann... 1 (stimme überhaupt nicht zu) 2 (stimme ...	Wert	14	
11	Andere Tools zur Unterstützung der Kommunikation und Reflektierter Praxis ...	Seitenende (Trennt Fragen)	0	
12	Welche andere Tools haben Sie verwendet, um mit Ihren Kollegen zu kommunizieren und sie zu unterstüt&u ...	offen	0	
13	Welche andere Tools haben Sie verwendet, um über Ihre Praxis zu reflektieren? ...	offen	0	
14	Allgemeine Zufriedenheit	Seitenende (Trennt Fragen)	0	
15	Was könnte man im Kurs verbessern? ...	offen	0	
16	Wie könnte man noch die EKT-Tools verbessern? ...	offen	0	

When you check that all looks good, go to 'open'/ publish the course, make it open to the users of the platform, and copy the link to the course.

Nº	Titel	Typ	Anzahl der Möglichkeiten	ändern
1	Land	Dropdown	5	
2	Geschlecht	Dropdown	3	
3	Alter	Dropdown	6	

In the 'normal' courses, go to the learning path, and create a new Document. There you can type the intro text to the survey, add logos, and insert the link to the Survey.

The link can be also sent to tutors. Or use another route. Important is that the participants log in to fill in the survey.

Supportive documents

Document with the links: <https://cumulo.cesga.es/index.php/s/EmaytJEGfQxHKQT>

Documents for translation: <https://cumulo.cesga.es/index.php/s/qSkJnGFmBeZAzYL>

8. APPENDIX B. EKT SPOC CERTIFICATE

Professional training certificate on Small Private Online Course (SPOC) for teachers, students and university lecturers of the European project:

*Improving Educational Innovation, competitiveness and quality of higher education through
collaboration between University and Companies (Educational Knowledge Transfer)*

(student teacher)

(SIGNATURE 1)

(University College of Teacher Education, Vienna
Vice-Rector)

(SIGNATURE 2)

(Project Manager)

It is hereby confirmed that the following person has attended the training course (SPOC) of the EU project Educational Knowledge Transfer, no. 2019-1-ES01-KA21-064187 of the strategic action Knowledge Alliances for Higher Education coordinated by the *University of Santiago de Compostela (USC)* and integrated by *Galicia Supercomputing Centre (CESGA)*, *Pädagogische Hochschule Wien (PHW)*, *die Berater (DB)*, *Marino Institute of Education (MIE)*, *H2 Learning (H2)*, *Universidade do Minho (UM)*, *Lusoinfo II Multimédia S.A (LIM)*, *BeezNest Belgium (BZN)*, *University of Plymouth (PLU)* with a length of 10 hours.

The following contents were addressed:

Unit 1. Introduction to the EKT platform 4 hours

Unit 2. Action research in the classroom 3 hours

Unit 3. Focusing on dialogue and personal reflection 3 hours

Project Partners

Universidade do Minho

Editor:

Santiago de Compostela: Grupo de investigación de
Tecnología Educativa (USC). <https://www.tecnoeduc.es/>